

**GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science:
Challenges in Higher Education**
Project Reference: 2024-1-ES01-KA220-HED-000246558
<https://ub.edu/GEDIS>

European Summer School in Information Science & Gender Barcelona: Open Educational Resources Report

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GEDIS
**Gender Diversity in Information Science:
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European Summer School in Information Science & Gender
Barcelona: Open Educational Resources Report

Barcelona, 25/10/2025

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1. Introduction

This report reflects the work undertaken by international students from the GEDIS project consortium who attended the European Summer School on Information Science and Gender (ESSISGEN) in Barcelona, held in September 2025. The preparation of this report reflects collaboration among students from different countries and cultures. All Open Educational Resources (OER) are first produced in one of the consortium’s languages, with derivative and translated versions prepared thereafter. The represented languages are Bosnian, Catalan, Croatian, Czech, English, German, and Spanish. Students first created an OER with colleagues from their own institution and later developed another with international peers. Consequently, the initial OERs were typically produced in one of the consortium’s languages, whereas the collaborative OERs with Summer School colleagues were prepared first in English as the common working language.

The Open Educational Resources (OERs) produced for the GEDIS Summer School held in Barcelona in September 2025 reflect a multidisciplinary and inclusive approach to digital education, technology, and gender equality within Library and Information Science (LIS) and related fields. Together, these twelve resources illustrate the School’s commitment to promoting critical reflection, interdisciplinarity, and innovation in teaching and learning through gender-sensitive and ethical frameworks.

The collection begins with “Open Data: Transparency vs. Trust,” which explores the relationship between openness, reliability, and public confidence in digital information systems. Complementing this, “Algorithmic Bias in AI” and “Hate Speech” address the ethical dimensions of artificial intelligence, highlighting how data-driven technologies reproduce social biases and inequalities. “Mind the Gap” serves as a

thematic bridge, examining gender gaps in STEM disciplines and their implications for inclusivity in digital education.

Resources such as “Supporting Women in Intro CSIT” and “Gaming & Gender” tackle gender stereotypes in computer science and gaming environments, promoting equitable participation and awareness of cultural representation in technological spaces. The OER “Translation and Gender” extends the debate to linguistic and cultural mediation, illustrating how gendered perspectives shape meaning across languages. “Cultural Heritage and Gender” further integrates feminist and heritage studies, encouraging reflection on whose narratives are preserved, represented, or excluded in digital archives.

At the intersection of ethics and freedom of expression, “Intellectual Freedom and Censorship” discusses challenges faced by information professionals in safeguarding access to knowledge. “User Experience” and “Human-Computer Interaction” highlight the importance of inclusive design principles, while “Students’ Perception on Using ChatGPT” introduces an empirical perspective on generative AI in education, reflecting the ongoing dialogue between human agency and machine learning. Finally, “Paradoxes of media and information literacy” shows different issues like the paradox of neutrality, trust and responsibility.

This set of OERs embodies the ESSISGEN Summer School’s mission to cultivate critical digital literacy, foster gender equality, and inspire reflective, responsible practices in the information professions. Each resource not only serves as a pedagogical tool but also as a catalyst for transformative learning and institutional change across Europe and beyond. All these OER are aimed at different audiences selected by the students. These are librarians, higher education professors and students. Nevertheless, any of the resources can be used and reused by all audiences and adapted to the relevant context.

2. List of Open Educational Resources

2.1. Open data: Transparency vs. Trust

First Version

Battle, Ariadna, Brtan, Lorena, Min, Hyerim, Osmanhodžić, Hajrija. 2025. "Open data: Transparency vs. Trust". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17067618>

Derivative works and translations

Osmanhodžić, Hajrija. 2025. "Otvoreni podaci: transparentnost naspram povjerenja". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17296500>

Min, Hyerim. 2025. "Offene Daten: Transparenz vs. Vertrauen". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17167032>

Brtan, Lorena. 2025. "Otvoreni podaci: Transparentnost vs Povjerenje". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17296399>

Battle, Ariadna. 2025. "Datos abiertos: Transparencia vs. Confianza". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17296254>

Battle, Ariadna, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Dades obertes: Transparència vs. Confiança”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17296634>

Varga, Izabela. 2025. “Otevřená data: Transparentnost vs. Důvěra”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17296556>

2.2. Algorithmic Bias in AI: Key Concepts, Implications, and Solutions

First version

Algorithmic Bias in AI: Key Concepts, Implications, and Solutions

This OER examines AI and algorithmic bias, its causes, and real-world impacts. It highlights the importance of human oversight and strategies to mitigate bias for fairer AI systems.

Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to systems that display intelligent behavior by analyzing their environment and taking actions – with some degree of autonomy – to achieve specific goals.

Algorithmic bias is a systematic error or unfair outcome produced by machine learning algorithms, often reflecting or reinforcing existing social, racial, or gender biases, caused by prejudiced assumptions in their design or by training on incomplete or distorted data.

Karmil, Kenza, Boskovic, Luka, Kartašová, Denisa. 2025. “Algorithmic Bias in AI: Key Concepts, Implications, and Solutions”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17067091>

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Derivative works and translations

San José, Claudia, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Biaix algorítmic en la IA: conceptes clau, implicacions i solucions”. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17306646>

San José, Claudia, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Sesgo algorítmico en la IA: conceptos clave, implicaciones y soluciones”. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17296079>

Kenza, Karmil. 2025. “Algorithmische Voreingenommenheit in der KI: Zentrale Konzepte, Implikationen und Lösungen”. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17166835>

Bošković, Luka. 2025. “Algoritamska pristranost u UI: Ključni pojmovi, implikacije, i rješenja”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17293326>

Bitunjac, Marija. 2025. “Algoritamska pristranost u umjetnoj inteligenciji: Ključni pojmovi, implikacije i rješenja”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17164519>

Kartašová, Denisa. 2025. “Algoritmická zaujatost v umělé inteligenci: Klíčové pojmy, dopady a řešení”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17302342>

2.3. Hate Speech & Misinformation: The real status or treatment of women within socialist contexts

First version

Hate Speech & Mis/Disinformation

The real status or treatment of women within socialist contexts

This open educational resource (OER) offers a historical perspective on the invisible façades of totalitarianism and the role of women within it. It aims to encourage critical reflection on the power of hate speech, misinformation and disinformation as tools of propaganda used to shape ideology and suppress dissent.

Target audiences: 📖 Librarians, 👨 Professors, 🎓 Students

1. KEY CONCEPTS (DEFINITIONS)

- Hate speech, misinformation, and disinformation are distinct forms of harmful speech
- No universally agreed-upon definitions for these terms
- Definitions vary across legal, academic, and policy contexts

Hate Speech

Any kind of communication in speech, writing, or behavior, that attacks or uses pejorative or discriminatory language with reference to a person or a group on the basis of who they are—in other words, based on their religion, ethnicity, nationality, race, color, descent, gender, or other identity factor.

Misinformation vs. Disinformation

Misinformation refers to the unintentional spread of false or misleading information, while disinformation is the deliberate creation and dissemination of falsehoods intended to cause harm.

Varbanova, Daniela, Gagulić, Kristina, Mulabećirović, Lejla. 2025. “Hate Speech & Misinformation: The real status or treatment of women within socialist contexts”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17067560>

Derivative works and translations

Batlle, Ariadna, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Discurso de odio y desinformación: El estatus real o el trato de las mujeres en contextos socialistas”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17293659>

Batlle, Ariadna, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. “Discurs d'odi i de desinformació”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17298272>

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Varbanova, Daniela. 2025. "Hassrede und Des-/Fehlinformation". Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17300493>

Mulabećirović, Lejla. 2025. "Govor mržnje i mis/dezinformacije: Pravi status ili tretman žena u socijalističkim kontekstima". Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17300553>

Gagulić, Kristina. 2025. "Govor mržnje i mis/dezinformacije". Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17300602>

Kartašová, Denisa. 2025. "Nenávistné projevy a mis/dezinformace: Skutečný stav nebo zacházení se ženami v rámci socialistických kontextů". Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17300649>

2.4. Mind the Gap: Gender Data and AI Bias

First Version

This OER comprises a poster and an evidence brief on the AI gender data gap – definition, causes, documented cases, and recommended interventions.

Mind the Gap: Gender Data and AI Bias

The gender data gap = missing/uneven data about women. As a result, AI decisions skew male through representative, algorithmic, cultural, and intersectional biases.

WHY IT HAPPENS

- Most AI teams are men; design choices reflect their blind spots.
- Training data under-represent women.
- Optimising only for overall accuracy or profit can sideline minorities.
- Women's phone/internet access is lower → fewer data traces.
- Binary labels and averages hides subgroups.

CASES BY BIAS TYPE

Representative

- Face recognition: 35% errors for darker-skinned women (0.8% lighter-skinned men).
- DALL-E 2 job images: women 38% (men 62%); women smiling 2.2x more.
- STEM visuals: 75–100% men.

Algorithmic

- Hiring AI: male-skewed training → women's CVs down-ranked.
- Credit scoring: women fewer/smaller loans despite better repayment.
- Health AI: misses women's symptoms → delayed diagnosis.
- Music recommenders: up to +6.3 pp more accurate for men.

Cultural

- Default female assistants → "women-as-helpers" stereotype.
- Llama-2 stories: women in domestic roles ~4x more; men get higher-status jobs.

Intersectional

- YouTube captions: more errors for women.
- STEM job ads: men → 20% impressions.
- Book recommenders: less exposure for women authors

CLOSING THE GAP: WHAT TO DO

Representative bias

- Inclusive datasets; document & publish coverage; intersectional benchmarks.

Algorithmic bias

- Remove gender markers from inputs; adjust decision thresholds to balance errors; debias in training and post-processing; continuous monitoring.

Cultural bias

- Neutral/non-binary default voices; design checks for stereotypes; diverse teams in design and testing.

Intersectional bias

- Publish subgroup metrics (gender, skin tone, age, dialect); pre/post-deployment audits; classify HR/finance as high-risk; gender impact statements; transparency standards.

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GEDIS project context

This resource is part of the European project GEDIS (Gender Diversity in Information Science), which promotes open educational tools to tackle gender inequalities in higher education, with an emphasis on disciplines related to Information and Library Science. This educational material was developed within the framework of the Summer School Barcelona, as part of the GEDIS project.

GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science: Challenges in Higher Education. <https://ub.edu/gedis>

Citation: Bosshammer, Svetlana and Daniela Varbanova. 2025. Mind the Gap: Gender Data and AI Bias. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17164102>

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Bosshammer, Svetlana, Varbanova, Daniela. 2025. "Mind the Gap: Gender Data and AI Bias". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17164102>

Derivative works and translations

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- Chlopčíková, Nela. 2025. "Pozor na mezeru: Genderová data a předsudky v AI". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333105>

2.5. Supporting Women in Intro CS/IT: First-Two-Weeks Faculty Playbook

First version

Supporting Women in Intro CS/IT

First-Two-Weeks Faculty Playbook

Target audiences: 🧑 Professors 🧑 Students

This open educational resource (OER) presents comparative data on gender representation in educational leadership across six European countries involved in the GEDIS project. Drawing on UNESCO's GEM Gender Report 2025, the infographic highlights disparities in the presence of women in ministerial positions, school leadership, and higher education management. The aim is to encourage critical reflection on gender inequalities in decision-making roles within the education sector.

Women in tech continue to face major inequality, from lower salaries and underrepresentation in leadership to limited access to venture capital. Despite claims of fair hiring and pay practices, real progress remains slow due to persistent barriers like stereotypes, lack of mentors, and pedagogical approaches. A practical toolkit with concrete strategies is essential to drive real change and foster a more inclusive tech industry.

Two-week Instructor Kit

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Bosshammer, Svetlana, Pemper, Inga, Bitunjac, Marija. 2025. "Supporting Women in Intro CS/IT: First-Two-Weeks Faculty Playbook". Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17067105>

Derivative works and translations

Battle, Ariadna, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. "Apoyando a las mujeres en cursos introductorios de Ciencias de la Computación/Tecnología de la Información: Manual para el profesorado para las dos primeras semanas". Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17293881>

Battle, Ariadna, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. "Donant suport a les dones en cursos introductoris de Ciències de la Computació/Tecnologia de la Informació". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17306577>

Bosshammer, Svetlana. 2025. "Frauen in Intro CS/IT unterstützen". Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17166593>

Osmanhodžić, Hajrija. 2025. "Podrška ženama u uvodnom CS/IT: Priručnik za nastavno osoblje za prve dvije sedmice". Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17285428>

Pemper, Inga. 2025. "Podrška ženama u računalnim znanostima/IT: Priručnik za nastavnike za prva dva tjedna". Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17285547>

Chlopčíková, Nela. 2025. "Podpora žen v Intro CS/IT: Příručka pro fakulty v prvních dvou týdnech". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17302283>

2.6. Gaming & Gender

First Version

GEDIS

Videoigre i spol

Ovaj OER prikazuje glavne izazove, prednosti i rješenja vezana uz spol i videoigre, s posebnim naglaskom na iskustva i prikazivanje žena. Ističe utjecaj stereotipa, seksizma i toksičnosti zajednice, ali i pozitivne učinke raznolikosti i inkluzivnog dizajna videoigara. Cilj mu je naglasiti ključne izazove, mogućnosti i rješenja vezana uz spol i videoigre kako bi se potaklo stvaranje inkluzivnijeg i kreativnijeg okruženja za sve igrače.

Povijest i kontekst

- industrija videoigara od samih početaka oblikovana u muškom okruženju - razvila kulturu u kojoj dominira muška perspektiva
- videoigre stvarane za mušku publiku
- razlike u navikama, motivacijama i iskustvima igranja

Prikaz žena u videoigrama

- nemoćni ili sekundarni likovi
- često prikazani u ulozi "damsel in distress"
- seksualizirani prikazi žena u videoigrama povezani s nižim samopouzdanjem igračica i jačanjem seksističkih stavova kod igrača

Izazovi

Stereotipi, toksično ponašanje, seksualizacija, stvaranje krivih percepcija...

Prednosti

Raznolikost, inkluzivnost, kreativnost, smanjivanje stereotipa, ravnopravnost...

Rješenja

Inkluzivni dizajn, promjene u industrijskoj praksi, edukacije i prevencije stereotipa

Ciljne grupe: Studentica

LITERATURA
Gibert-Pérez, Aïa, Manuel Martí-Vilà, Cesar Merino-Soto, Guillermo M. Chens, i Laura Badenes-Ribera. 2024. Gender differences in internet gaming among university students: a discriminant analysis. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/psp.2024.14127.1>
Park, Hyeon. 2023. Video Games and Gender Equality: How Has Video Gaming Become a Male Privilege? DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2196/2023.10561523023045>

Veza sa GEDIS projektom
Ovaj je resurs dio evropskog projekta GEDIS (Gender Diversity in Information Science), koji promiče otvorene obrazovne alate za sučeljenje rodne nejednakosti u visokoškolskom obrazovanju, s naglaskom na discipline povezane s informacijama i komunikacijskim znanostima. Ovaj je obrazovni materijal nastao u okviru Ljetne škole u Barceloni, kao dio projekta GEDIS.

GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science: Challenges in Higher Education. <https://ub.edu/gedis>
Ciljanje: Gagulić, Kristina, Inga Pemper, Antonio Prgomet, 2025. Videoigre i spol. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17315482

Sufinancirano od strane Europske unije. Imenoma navedenja i stvarni inkluzivno su odgovornost autora i ne odražavaju nužno stavove Europske unije niti Španjolske službe za internacionalizaciju obrazovanja (SEPIE). Europska unija, niti tijela koja dodjeljuje sredstva, ne mogu se smatrati odgovornim za njih.

Gagulić, Kristina, Pemper, Inga, Prgomet, Antonio. 2025. "Videoigre i spol". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17315482>

Derivative works and translations

Gagulić, Kristina, Pemper, Inga, Prgomet, Antonio. 2025. "Gaming & Gender". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17315515>

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San José, Claudia, Boté-Vericad, Juan-José. 2025. "Videojuegos y Género". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17332914>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333002>.

Kartašová, Denisa. 2025. "Videohry & Gender". Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333030>

2.7. Translation and Gender

First version

Translation and Gender

This OER explores the intersections of translation and gender, focusing on feminist translation practices, gendered language, and cross-linguistic challenges. It aims to help students critically engage with language and develop inclusive translation strategies.

Target audience: Students

Feminist Translation	Traditional Translation	LLM Translation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ideological act; translator = rewriter • Example: "...without opening legs" • Strategies: supplementing, prefacing/footnoting, hijacking • Challenges patriarchy → empowers women, develops language 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neutral, faithful copy; passive, inferior • Example: "...without pulling up skirt" • Metaphors of reproduction, control, violence • Maintains patriarchal stereotypes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most systems default to masculine forms in ambiguous cases. • Systems default to stereotypical gender roles in professions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Doctor → doctor (masculine) ◦ Nurse → enfermera (feminine) • Machine translation can reflect and even exacerbate existing biases. • Responsibility of translators and developers: develop strategies for more neutral and inclusive translations.

Gendered	vs.	Gender-Neutral
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chairman Firman Polísiman 	→	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chairperson Firefighter Police officer
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bilimčan (science man) 	→	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bilim insani (science person)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Studenten Lehrer 	→	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Studierende Lehrkräfte
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zdravotni sestra (man working as a nurse) 	→	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zdravotni sestra / bratr (just a nurse)

Cross-linguistic Gender Challenges

- Translation = more than words. It shapes and reproduces gender ideologies.
- Translators = not neutral mediators. They are active agents making ideological choices.
- Choices in pronouns, inclusivity, visibility = political acts

LLM – Strategies

- Gender-neutral adjectives (e.g., forms for both masculine and feminine).
- Neuter case adjectives (use of neuter grammar in Icelandic/Czech).
- Part of speech change (using a noun phrase instead of an adjective).
- English borrowing (keeping the adjective in English).
- Alternative morphology (e.g., in Spanish replacing -o/-a with @).

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This resource is part of the European project GEDIS (Gender Diversity in Information Science), which promotes open educational tools to tackle gender inequalities in higher education, with an emphasis on disciplines related to Information and Library Science. This educational material was developed within the framework of the Summer School Barcelona, as part of the GEDIS project.

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Koçlu, Burcu, Prgomet, Antonio, Varga, Izabela. 2025. "Translation and Gender". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17062711>

Derivative works and translations

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2.8. Cultural Heritage and Gender

First Version

Cultural Heritage and Gender

This project explores how cultural heritage, particularly in the field of literature, has historically marginalized women (authors) and their works. It highlights forgotten female voices and proposes strategies to ensure a more inclusive cultural memory for future generations – canon revision, re-editions, translations, and digital projects.

Target audiences: 🎓 Students

- Introduction + historically imbalanced canon
- Forgotten voices and their rediscovery
- The present, libraries and the audience

legacy compiled of artifacts and attributes of a particular group or society

draws from the past and aims to benefit the future generations

concept of cultural heritage is changing based on current cultural systems and their values

Chlopčíková, Nela, Kartašová, Denisa, Varga, Izabela. 2025. “Cultural Heritage and Gender”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17145145>

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Derivative works and translations

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2.9. Intellectual freedom and censorship

First version

Intellectual freedom and censorship

Intellectual freedom is the **right to access, explore, and express** ideas without restriction. Censorship, by contrast, involves the **suppression or control** of information, often limiting open dialogue and critical thinking.

PROFESSORS

- Book bans are seen as a **threat to freedom of expression** and **educational diversity**.
- Book bans **limit access** to important literature.
- Professors often feel pressured to skip controversial topics, limiting discussions that **build critical thinking and empathy**.

STUDENTS

- Narrowed learning scope negatively impacting the **development of critical thinking**.
- **Distrust** in the information that is accessible.
- Feelings of invisibility and **compromised self-expression**.

Most frequently censored topics:

- LGBTQ+
- Racial issues
- Cultural and religious content
- Political content

What role do we play, individually, in defending intellectual freedom?

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GEDIS project context

This resource is part of the European project GEDIS (Gender Diversity in Information Science), which promotes open educational tools to tackle gender inequalities in higher education, with an emphasis on disciplines related to Information and Library Science. This educational material was developed within the framework of the Summer School Barcelona, as a part of the GEDIS project.

GEDIS - Gender Diversity in Information Science: Challenges in Higher Education. <https://ub.edu/gedis>

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Co-funded by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are solely those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Spanish Service for the Internationalisation of Education (SEPE). Neither the EU nor the granting authority can be held responsible.

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2.10. User Experience: UX

First Version

GEDIS **EXPERIÈNCIA D'USUARI: UX**

L'UX és l'estudi de la interacció que fa un usuari amb un producte o recurs, per tal de proporcionar una experiència que engloba:

Usabilitat, accesibilitat, utilitat, credibilitat, facilitat, deseabilitat

Etapas del procès:

- Mètodes d'indagació**
 - Entrevista
 - Grups focals
 - Enquestes
 - Benchmarking
 - Traçabilitat
- Disseny conceptual**
 - Perfil d'usuari
 - Necessitat/Problema
 - Escenari
- Arquitectura de la informació**
 - Avaluació de sistemes
 - Etiquetatge
 - Navegació
 - Cerca
 - Inventari de continguts
 - Card sorting
 - Tree test
 - Arbre de continguts
- Prototipatge**
 - Sketches
 - Flowchart
 - Wireframes
- Avaluació**
 - Test amb usuaris

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2.11. Human-Computer-Interaction: Fundamentals and Applications

First Version

The thumbnail shows the cover of the OER. It features the GEDIS logo on the left. The title 'Human-Computer-Interaction: Fundamentals and Applications' is prominently displayed in the center. Below the title, a short description states: 'This OER introduces the fundamental concepts, principles, and methods of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI), aiming to guide students in designing digital systems that are user-friendly, accessible, and effective'. The target audience is identified as 'Students'. The cover is divided into two main sections: 'What is HCI?' and 'Why is HCI important?'. The 'What is HCI?' section, by Dengen 2025, lists three bullet points: HCI is a multidisciplinary field focused on the design and use of computer technologies; it studies how people interact with devices via touch, voice, gestures, eye movement, and more; and it explores how machines are designed to respond to these interactions. The 'Why is HCI important?' section, also by Dengen 2025, lists three bullet points: HCI aims to create natural, intuitive, and enjoyable user experiences – not just functional ones; it focuses on human senses, thoughts, and behaviors as the foundation for design; and effective systems require understanding how humans interpret, decide, and act. Human-centered design ensures systems adapt to natural human tendencies.

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2.13. Paradoxes of Media and Information Literacy

GEDIS

Paradoksi medijske i informacijske pismenosti

Paradoks normativnosti:
Pismenost nije univerzalna - živi unutar konteksta.
Kako povezati demokratiju, kulturu participacije i pismenost?

Paradoks odgovornosti:
Prijenos odgovornosti s institucija na pojedince.
Može li pojedinac izdržati SVE odgovornosti današnjice?

Paradoks povjerenja:
Da li svi žele biti racionalni i informisani?
Kako graditi povjerenje podučavanjem sumnje?

Vremenski paradoks:
Kako podučavati i predviđati tehnologije budućnosti?
Historijski kontekst sredstava i navika informisanja.

Paradoks neutralnosti:
Inherentna političnost informacije i znanja.
Medijska i informacijska pismenost nije neutralna u represivnim društvima!

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Povezanost sa projektom GEDIS
Ovaj resurs je dio evropskog projekta GEDIS (Gender Diversity in Information Science), koji promovira upotrebu otvorenih obrazovnih alata za rješavanje rodne nejednakosti u visokom obrazovanju, s fokusom na područje povezano sa bibliotečkim i informacijskim naukama. Ovaj obrazovni materijal nastao je u okviru Ujedinjene škole u Barceloni, kao dio projekta GEDIS.

Ciljne grupe:
Bibliotekarike, Nastavnici/ice, Studentice

First version

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